

Machine Learning for High-Resolution Soil-Sealing Mapping: Opportunities and Challenges

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Abstract

Soil sealing poses major environmental risks, especially in Flanders, Belgium, where sealing rates are among the highest in Europe. We present an automated methodology for producing annual soil-sealing maps at 1-m resolution by integrating administrative datasets with machine-learning-based classification of high-resolution aerial imagery. Temporal correction is applied to reduce year-to-year inconsistencies. The resulting maps achieve an overall accuracy of 97.8% and show an increase in sealing rate from 14.2% in 2013 to 15.7% in 2023. Operational challenges include evolving administrative source data, incomplete detection of large homogeneous surfaces, the labour-intensive nature of training-data creation, and model drift and change detection issues due to varying imagery characteristics. Methodological refinements, retraining and data harmonisation improved recent estimates. Structural limitations of visible-spectrum imagery motivate future integration of higher-resolution and complementary spectral data to further enhance the method's robustness.

Keywords: machine learning, soil sealing, remote sensing, high resolution, Flanders

1. Introduction

Soil sealing is defined as the area where the nature and/or condition of the soil surface has been altered by placing artificial, (semi-)impermeable materials from buildings, roads, constructions ... (see Jones et al. 2012). Soil sealing increases flood risk, limits water infiltration, intensifies urban heat island effects, reduces carbon storage and leads to biodiversity loss. The Flanders region in Belgium has one of the highest soil sealing rates in Europe (EEA 2020), making it particularly vulnerable to these impacts. This underscores the need for sustainable spatial management, which in turn requires precise and timely monitoring to guide policy measures. The rapid growth of data, coupled with increasing temporal and spatial resolution, offers unprecedented opportunities for geographical analysis and decision-making. Machine learning and artificial intelligence provide powerful tools for processing these complex datasets and obtaining insights. However, these technologies are not stand-alone solutions. Ancillary data sources often remain crucial for ensuring meaningful and reliable outcomes. Moreover, substantial human intervention and expertise are

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frequently required for preparing and validating input data for automated systems.

Interest in quantifying and mapping sealed surfaces and their spatial evolution has increased significantly in recent years. Sources used for measuring soil sealing at the national or regional level include satellite and aerial images (EEA, Hungary, Italy, Spain), cadastral data (Austria), spatial planning documents (Latvia), Corine Land Cover maps (Czech Republic) and field survey, census data or ground-based data collection (Bispo et al. 2025). For Flanders, we developed a method that automatically integrates “known” sealing from administrative sources with modelled sealing generated through machine learning, resulting in annual soil-sealing maps (ASSMs).

2. Data

2.1. Administrative Soil Sealing

The administrative soil sealing was derived from the buildings, roads, railways and water-bodies vector layers of Flanders’ Base Map (GRB) from Digitaal Vlaanderen. As of June 2023, the Road Register dataset (Wegenregister) has been integrated into GRB. This led to a 65% increase in the number of registered kilometres and to a different categorisation of sealing (‘fixed’, ‘loose’, ‘mixed’). Only road segments with ‘fixed sealing’ were selected for consistency with previous datasets. Road segments with ‘loose’ or ‘mixed sealing’ could still be detected as ‘sealed’ by the modelling.

2.2. Modelled Soil Sealing

The modelled soil sealing was based on annual winter RGB orthophotos with a 25-cm resolution from Digitaal Vlaanderen. Machine learning models were developed for this purpose, including a separate model for port areas, which were defined by overlapping the legal boundaries of the seaports with Flanders’ industrial parks from VLAIO.

The modelling results were not reliable in 1) blurred areas in the aerial imagery and 2) beaches and dunes (from the 2023 ASSM onwards). For some years, the modelling incorrectly classified relatively large parts of beach and dune areas as ‘sealed’. Hence, these areas were selected from the 2023 Biological Valuation Map (BWK) from INBO. As of 2016, sensitive sites such as military bases and nuclear power plants have been blurred in the orthophotos, which distorts the models. As the blurred areas were not adequately identified for the initial ASSMs, they have been manually mapped from the 2023 ASSM onwards, based on colour variations in the aerial images.

3. Methods

3.1. Administrative Soil Sealing

Soil sealing in Flanders was derived each year using a hierarchical decision tree classifying each 1-m pixel as ‘sealed’ or ‘unsealed’ (*Figure 1*). First, information from Flanders’ Base Map was processed into the administrative soil sealing. All water was labelled ‘unsealed’, while buildings, roads and railways were considered ‘sealed’. Unlike the water and building layers, the road and railway data required additional processing (Cockx et al. 2025). In the decision-making chain, this administrative information (in the order of water, buildings, roads and railroads) was given priority over the modelled output for the corresponding pixels (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1. Overview of the sequential steps for generating the annual soil-sealing map for Flanders. The thick arrows indicate the order of the decision-making process for classifying a pixel as ‘sealed’ or ‘unsealed’.

3.2. Modelled Soil Sealing

Available administrative databases do not cover all soil sealing. Sources of soil sealing that are often not present in administrative data include for example some parking areas, private driveways and garden terraces. To detect these remaining sealed surfaces, two machine learning models were built using the convolutional neural network model U-Net (Ronneberger et al. 2015) for semantic segmentation. Initially, a global model was developed for the whole of Flanders. As this model performed less well in port areas, an additional port-specific model was defined for detecting sealing that was overlooked by the global model.

For a subset of the aerial images, the sealed sections were manually labelled. 70% of the labelled images were used as the training set for the models. The remaining 30% served as a test set for validating the models’ results. The models produced a sealing probability map, which was converted into a binary modelled sealing map. The final modelled soil-sealing map was obtained by combining the binary maps from the two models in some areas and disregarding them in others. For the port areas, both binary maps were compared. If at least one map identified a pixel as ‘sealed’, this became the final label. For the rest of Flanders outside the seaports, only the global model’s classification was taken into account.

For both sensitive sites (military areas, nuclear power stations, etc.) and beaches and dunes (from the 2023 ASSM onwards), the model results were disregarded and all pixels were labelled ‘unsealed’. Since information on water, buildings, roads and railways is given priority in the allocation (*Figure 1*) and other soil sealing in these zones is limited or absent, this produces usable results for these areas.

The time series of the final modelled soil-sealing maps revealed that two changes for a pixel over a two-year period were almost always the result of inaccuracies. A temporal correction was therefore applied to eliminate these discrepancies and obtain temporal continuity (*Table 1*). If a pixel’s label for the previous and following year was the same, but differed for the year considered, that pixel was corrected. In all other cases, the original classification was retained.

<u>corrected</u>	original	original	<u>corrected</u>
<i>t-1</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>t+1</i>	<i>t</i>
<i>unsealed</i>	sealed	sealed	sealed
sealed	<i>unsealed</i>	<i>unsealed</i>	<i>unsealed</i>
<i>unsealed</i>	sealed	<i>unsealed</i>	→ <i>unsealed</i>
sealed	<i>unsealed</i>	sealed	→ sealed

Table 1. Correction of the labels of year t 's modelled soil-sealing map for temporal continuity.

3.3. Annual Soil-Sealing Map

In the final step, the administrative and modelled soil sealing were combined into an annual soil-sealing map (*Figure 1*). In this process, the administrative soil sealing took precedence over the modelled information when classifying areas as ‘sealed’ or ‘unsealed’. The resulting ASSMs’ accuracy was determined using the same test set as for the model validation.

4. Results

The methodology produced an ASSM with a 1-m resolution from the base year 2013 onwards² (*Figure 2*). The validation of the ASSMs yielded an overall accuracy of 97.8%. For the 2023 ASSM, the administrative soil sealing classified 8.4% of Flanders as ‘sealed’, two-thirds of which was based on building data. The modelling identified 7.3% of Flanders’ area as ‘sealed’. Based on the ASSMs, soil sealing in Flanders rose from 14.2% in 2013 to 15.7% in 2023 (*Figure 3*). This is a net increase of 21,110 ha (+11.0%), corresponding to a sealing rate of 5.8 ha/day.

Figure 2. 2020 annual soil-sealing map (blue) on top of the corresponding winter orthophoto of Mechelen.

² Jaarlijkse bodemafdekkingskaart Vlaanderen (JaarBAK): vlaanderen.be/datavindplaats/catalogus?q.LIKE=JaarBAK%201%20m

Figure 3. Sealed surface evolution in Flanders between 2013 and 2023 (in ha, proportions in %).

5. Discussion

5.1. Model Retraining and Data Harmonisation

In 2025, the methodology was refined to counter a few shortcomings and data challenges (Cockx et al. 2025). When the model was applied beyond its initial training period (post-2020), the estimated extent of sealed surfaces in Flanders unexpectedly stopped increasing. This counterintuitive outcome appeared to reflect a systematic limitation of the machine-learning approach. To address this issue, additional labelling on more recent imagery was used to retrain and improve the model’s performance.

Several changes in input data further complicated the process. In 2023, a more comprehensively registered road network – including a revised definition of “sealed road” – was incorporated into Flanders’ Base Map without retroactive application. In addition, colour distribution shifts in the 2024 aerial images led to model drift. These colour differences were corrected using a principal component analysis, with the previous year’s imagery serving as a reference. Thanks to these refinements, approximately 1,500 hectares of sealed surfaces that had likely been missed earlier were identified in the 2023 annual soil-sealing map.

5.2. Local Inconsistencies and Change Detection

Despite high global accuracy at the scale of Flanders, local inconsistencies remained. Large homogeneous sealed surfaces – particularly in ports and industrial areas – were still incompletely detected. To mitigate this issue, an additional port-specific model was trained. Yet full coverage remains challenging both inside and outside port areas.

Other factors further limit change-detection accuracy. The absence of reliable, up-to-date information on non-permanent coverings in agricultural areas hinders accurate temporal comparisons. Moreover, variations in capture time and angle between annual aerial photographs introduce artefacts such as shadows and seasonal vegetation effects. These temporary factors may produce apparent changes in sealed surfaces even when no actual physical modification occurred.

5.3. Future Directions and Structural Limitations

Currently, a 2.5-cm dataset is being tested to assess whether it can further improve model accuracy and be integrated into the existing workflow. While the increased level of detail introduces additional complexity and reveals features that were previously negligible, it also creates opportunities to better distinguish between sealed and unsealed surfaces.

Nonetheless, some limitations are structural. Producing training data remains time- and labour-intensive. In addition, the AI model relies exclusively on visible-spectrum imagery. Hence, surfaces invisible to the human eye – such as concrete covered by a thin layer of sand – cannot be detected, even at higher spatial resolutions. Complementary data sources, including infrared imagery, hold promise by providing additional information on surface properties. Ensuring that such datasets are available annually and at low or no cost would be essential for their operational integration and for further strengthening the methodology.

6. Conclusions

Our automated method produces accurate annual soil-sealing maps by complementing information from administrative sources with machine-learning output. This results in a consistent time series of 1-m resolution maps available from 2013 onward, showing that Flanders' sealing rate increased from 14.2% in 2013 to 15.7% in 2023. Following a refinement of the method, we are now evaluating the potential of 2.5-cm resolution imagery to further enhance its performance. We however remain dependent on human expertise and synchronised ancillary data. In short, our results show that artificial intelligence enables high-resolution geographical mapping and monitoring for large areas.

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